

Diversifying Professional Roles in Data Science

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The interdisciplinary nature of the data science workforce extends beyond the traditional notion of a "data scientist." A successful data science team requires a wide range of technical expertise, domain knowledge and leadership capabilities. To strengthen such a team-based approach, this policy briefing recommends that institutions, funders and policymakers invest in developing and professionalising diverse roles, fostering a resilient data science ecosystem for the future.

By recognising the diverse specialist roles that collaborate within interdisciplinary teams, organisations can leverage deep expertise across multiple skill sets, enhancing responsible decision-making and fostering innovation at all levels. Ultimately, this policy briefing seeks to shift the perception of data science professionals from the conventional view of individual data scientists to a competency-based model of specialist roles within a team, each essential to the success of data science initiatives.

Background

The UK Parliamentary Research Briefing on Digital Skills and Careers (April 2024) has highlighted the importance of digital skills across various sectors and identified a growing demand for specialised skills, particularly in data science and AI, which is rapidly outpacing supply, adding further to the UK's skills gap. This shortage of data science talents has been compounded by a lack of clarity in defining data science roles and corresponding skill requirements. The National Data Strategy (2019-2022) further highlighted the lack of widely agreed-upon definition of "data skills", which has led to inconsistencies in how roles are described across different industries.

Several efforts have been made to address these requirements and meet the growing demand for strengthening data science professional capabilities in the UK and internationally. For instance, the Alliance for Data Science Professionals, a multi-organisation group in the UK, has developed data science professionals standards [1] (AfDSP standards) to guide the professional accreditation of data science roles by defining five different 'skill areas' and pairing them with evidential requirements as professional responsibilities. Similarly, a recent publication for professionals working in Artificial Intelligence (AI), AI Skills for Business Competency Framework [2], by the Turing's Skills Team provides the 'Persona' describing a range of professional responsibilities undertaken by data scientists in AI. These standards provide a comprehensive overview of the various skills and expertise required throughout the life cycle of a data science initiative, rather than suggesting an all-encompassing role for a "data scientist".

Data science is a collaborative effort; therefore, the collective competencies across the entire team should be developed and leveraged appropriately, rather than focusing only on the technical skills attributed to a unicorn data scientist. The specific skills required for any data science initiative depend on the discipline, industry, and the context within which data-informed solutions are developed. Therefore, effective data science teams should be composed of diverse specialists who can flexibly combine their expertise to develop innovative solutions that address both societal and industry needs.

[1] Alliance for Data Science Professionals Standards (2022). alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk//standards

[2] The Alan Turing Institute, Innovate UK, DSIT, Digital Catapult, Science and Technology Facilities Council, British Standards Institution, & Alliance for Data Science.

AI Skills for Business Competency Framework (2024). Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11092677

Skills needed across the different stages of a project lifecycle also vary, with specific skills required at certain stages rather than throughout the project. Consequently, additional insights and examples about the data science team dynamics are necessary to clarify the diverse roles and responsibilities undertaken by a team of data science professionals and guide the specialisation of individuals in specific skill areas rather than attempting to build proficiency across all areas. Using the skill areas outlined in the AfDSP standards and the AI professional persona as starting points in this note, and providing examples from The Alan Turing Institute, we put forward recommendations to support the professionalisation of different specialist roles.

Fundamental Skills to Address Complex Challenges in Data Science

In the ever-evolving landscape of data science and AI, the standardisation of data practices and methods is increasingly more complex and challenging. To drive forward high-impact data-led and data-informed solutions, specialists within the data science team have to prioritise major interrelated issues encompassing 1) the use of high-quality, evidence-based methods, 2) impact on environment and data science ecosystem, 3) collaboration across experts in the field, and 4) inclusion of public interest and diverse societal considerations. We discuss each of these aspects below by highlighting fundamental skills such as scientific integrity, sustainability approaches, interdisciplinary collaboration, and Equality, Diversity, Inclusion and Accessibility (EDIA) principles, respectively.

1) Scientific Integrity: The discourse around the **reproducibility crisis** [3] over the last decade has raised awareness of the need for more transparency, reproducibility and trust

in data and AI systems. Evidence-based good practices in data science help improve the overall quality, validity and uptake of scientific outputs. **Open science** is leading the way in promoting scientific integrity [4]; however, the potential of implementing open and responsible methods across data initiatives is currently underutilised. Specialist roles like data wranglers, research software engineers, research community managers and data stewards embed these practices, contributing to building high-quality **open source** tools, **reproducible** methods and accessible infrastructure.

2) Sustainability Approaches: The urgency for strengthening sustainability practices in research involves addressing two kinds of sustainability: 1) sustainable approaches to minimise the negative environmental impact of data science, and 2) cost-effectiveness for the long-term sustainability of data science resources and infrastructure. To address this twofold issue, researchers must adopt methods that minimise environmental harm and implement best practices for discoverability and responsible data reuse, such as through implementing **FAIR and CARE principles** [5]. These practices can be championed and guided by specialised roles such as data wranglers, data stewards, librarians and sustainability experts.

3) Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Data science is by nature **interdisciplinary** and requires deliberate knowledge exchange through collaboration between different disciplines of experts across domains and often across sectors.

[3] Antunes, B., & Hill, D. R. C. (2024). Reproducibility, Replicability and Repeatability: A survey of reproducible research. *Computer Science Review*, 53, doi: [10.1016/j.cosrev.2024.100655](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2024.100655)

[4] European Commission, [The EU's open science policy](https://ec.europa.eu/euro-iss/comm-communication-2024-100655).

[5] Carroll, S.R., Herczog, E., Hudson, M. et al. Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures. *Sci Data* 8, 108 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>

Alongside data science specialists, it is important to involve domain specialists, policymakers, funders, government and the public at different stages of research to make it as impactful and responsible as possible. This aspect of data science often deals with the complexities of working across teams within and outside organisations, which can be addressed by roles such as research community managers, public engagement and citizen science practitioners who involve the right stakeholders throughout the data and AI systems lifecycle.

4) EDIA principles: From project design and development to the deployment of data and AI solutions, as well as the monitoring of their real-world impacts, EDIA principles should be integrated at every stage of a project lifecycle. Unlike some of the previously discussed challenges, the responsibility for embedding EDIA should be a shared one. All members of the data science team, as well as potential users and members of the public, should have the opportunity to engage with and participate in the process, improving usability and ethical implications of data science and minimising biases and societal harms that may arise from poorly considered data science approaches.

Addressing these interconnected issues requires fostering a strong foundation in the ethical and responsible use of data science and AI, which can be further strengthened by ethicists and social scientists within the team.

Recognition and Rewards for Specialist Roles: Institutional recognition and rewards aligned with the professional needs of emerging data science roles are critical to the success of data science institutions. Traditional definitions and assessment criteria for data scientists, which largely overlook the collective contributions made by different roles as part of a team, are no longer fit for purpose. As the field of data science evolves, so too must the frameworks for evaluating

and rewarding different expertise. Changes in professional recognition and reward systems must reflect the full spectrum of diverse contributions in data science made by specialist roles like data wranglers, research software engineers, community managers, data stewards and data/AI ethicists. By valuing and diversifying recognised and well-supported career pathways, institutions can build more resilient teams that are incentivised to collaborate and adapt to the emerging needs of data science.

In a separate publication, we have documented different roles associated with data science and AI in industries and academia: DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13242360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13242360).

Informing a Data Science Team Approach: Example from The Alan Turing Institute

The Alan Turing Institute, the UK's National Institute for Data Science and AI, was founded in 2015 with a clear mission [6]: 'To make great leaps in the development and use of data science and AI to change the world for the better'. Since its inception, the Turing has engaged with data science and AI research across a wide range of domains and collaborated with external stakeholders from across different sectors, including academia, government, the third sector, and industry.

The Turing Institute facilitates collaborations by convening cross-sector partners, combining their skills, expertise, and perspectives to pose questions and explore effective solutions together. The scale, intricacies and interdisciplinary nature of these projects require different specialist roles to be involved alongside specific domain expertise and supported to combine their skills, knowledge and leadership across areas such as data science, engineering, community engagement and project management.

[6] The Alan Turing Institute's Strategy, Published in 2023: <https://web.archive.org/web/20240614160034/https://www.turing.ac.uk/about-us/our-strategy>.

To enable this **team science** approach [7], projects at the Turing leverage specialist roles, adjusting team composition to achieve skills that can effectively respond to specific questions, objectives, intended outcomes, and real-world impacts of data science and AI.

Spotlight 1

The core capability teams at the Turing

- **Research Engineering Group (REG)** includes a team of Research Data Scientists, Research Software Engineers and Research Computing Engineers.
- **The Research Community Managers and Research Application Managers** work with diverse stakeholders of data science projects within and outside the organisation.
- **Data for Research** is a team that specialises in **data wrangling and data stewardship**.
- **Ethics and responsible innovation team**, which are part of the Public Policy programme and includes Applied AI and Research Ethicists.
- **The Programme Management Unit** consists of Research Project and Programme Managers.

The Alan Turing Institute has invested in establishing specialist roles and supporting them in strengthening their professional identity as part of “core capability teams” (Spotlight 1). Members of these core capability teams join data science projects to combine their specialist skills with the domain expertise drawn from various research and infrastructure programmes at the institute.

Persona of a Data Science Professional

An overarching persona of a Data Science and AI Professional that broadly defines all the responsibilities that are ideally shared by the data science team has been developed (Spotlight 2). This persona is based on the AI Professionals persona described in the AI Skills for Business Competency Framework.

[7] BBSRC mobilises team science to improve UK research culture. (2024, November). <https://www.ukri.org/news/bbsrc-mobilises-team-science-to-improve-uk-research-culture>

Spotlight 2

Overarching Persona for Data Science and AI Professionals

Data Science and AI professionals specialise in the field of data science and/or AI. Their responsibilities within an organisation concern the design, development, management and deployment of data and AI technologies.

- Data Science and AI Professionals will possess competency in the design, creation, deployment and maintenance of responsible data and AI-based systems.
- They will possess specialist knowledge in one or more subdiscipline(s) of Data Science and AI, like Computer Science, Statistics, Modelling, Machine Learning and Robotics.
- They possess a strong awareness of legal, ethical, regulatory and compliance considerations and know how to translate these into their roles.
- They are conversant in operating in settings of technical complexity and uncertainty.
- They will be aware of the risks of AI technology and will know the steps required to mitigate these within their role. They will be able to work with other specialists to understand and mitigate risks.
- They can interface effectively with AI Leaders to communicate the correctness of their technical solutions, as well as frame new data science and AI-based opportunities appropriately to inform the decision-making in their organisation.

In a detailed case study we have described personas for different specialist roles working within data science teams at The Alan Turing Institute [8]. Personas include Data science domain experts, Data science leaders, and Cross-cutting Research Infrastructure Specialists, also known as **Research Technical Professionals (RTPs)** [9].

[8] Karoune, E., & Sharan, M. (2024). Data Science Team Personas: Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11658994>

[9] Technicians and technology and skills specialists. (2023, August). <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/developing-people-and-skills/bbsrc/investing-in-research-teams>

RTPs at the Turing include Research Data Scientists, Research Software Engineers, Research Computing and Infrastructure Engineers, Research Community Managers, Research Application Managers, Data Wranglers, Research and AI Ethicists, Public Engagement Practitioners and Project & Programme Managers.

Skills and Competencies of Specialist Roles: Example from Research Community Management

To fully understand each data science specialist's role, we need to describe their skills and competencies, which include learned abilities, knowledge and professional behaviours. Skills and competency for emerging roles in data science will deepen employers' and employees' knowledge, guiding the development of a strong data science workforce.

Here, we provide a detailed example for Research Community Managers (RCMs), which can serve as a template for articulating skills and competency for other newly emerging roles.

RCMs work with different AI and data science projects and their communities, ensuring that collaborations amongst diverse stakeholders are effective and impactful. They involve all community members in defining challenges, developing milestones, integrating industry best practices and co-creating solutions that they can all benefit from. They connect data, software and expertise from projects across the institute while engaging researchers meaningfully with each other's work. As data science professionals, RCMs themselves bring specific data science skills that are defined in the AfDSP standards.

There are two core competencies, **communication and engagement**, where RCMs provide specific expertise and leadership with data science teams.

Additionally, RCMs bring knowledge across three peripheral competencies: strategic development, technical expertise and management skills for accountability (Spotlight 3). These skills are required to fulfill responsibilities for their roles but often involve collaboration with other specialists.

Specifically, RCMs contribute to matching the overall skills make-up of the team by either 1) directly bringing expertise through their core competencies, or 2) identifying and involving other collaborators in fulfilling other skill areas through their peripheral competencies.

Spotlight 3

RCM Skills and Competency Framework

Research Community Management: Skills and Competency Framework

Figure 1. The RCM Skills and Competency Framework outlines the roles and responsibilities associated with two sets of core competencies that RCMs lead (labelled in green). These competencies align with skill areas C and E from the AfDSP standards. Additionally, three sets of peripheral competencies, where RCMs collaborate with other specialists, correspond to the remaining skill areas (A, B, and D).

The detailed RCM Skills and Competency Framework has been published (Sharan & Karoune, 2023, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8337627](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8337627)) and a detailed description has been provided in a position paper on professionalising RCM roles in research institutions (Sharan, Karoune, *et. al.*, 2024, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.00108v1>).

As shown in Figure 1, the two core competencies for RCMs align with the AfDSP standards' skill area C: Problem Definition and Communication with Stakeholders, and skill area E: Evaluation and Reflection.

The skills and responsibilities outlined in the core and peripheral competencies of the RCM Skills and Competency Framework build on existing community management resources and incorporate real-world examples from the RCM team at the Turing Institute. This framework offers a comprehensive understanding of the professional roles of RCMs and highlights the competencies and skills of other specialist roles within a data science team.

Policy recommendations

Each specialist role in a data science team carries out both distinct and overlapping sets of responsibilities required for the successful execution of a data science project. They take leadership across different areas of data science projects while utilising their collective expertise and embedding best practices from across the ecosystem.

Below are five policy recommendations drawn from extensive research on professionalising diverse data science roles:

1. Development and documentation of skills and competencies for each specialist role should be supported. This development will have a significant impact on institutional and team capacity to identify and understand the right combination of roles needed across different data science initiatives and fill the data science skills gap.

2. Training and upskilling opportunities should be created to support data professionals in building the right skillset and apply them using team science approach.

By developing diverse skills and fostering collaboration within data science teams, Institutions can cultivate the necessary talent to address specific challenges, ultimately producing open, reproducible, and ethical data systems and technologies applicable to broader problems.

3. National and international standards for recognition and rewards should be evolved to match the expertise specialist roles bring into a data science ecosystem. Right incentives will enable institutions to leverage the combined expertise of all members within a team while providing the right career pathways for each of them.

4. The dynamics of interdisciplinary teams at various stages of a data science project should be evaluated. Interdisciplinary teams have the potential to rapidly adapt their working practices based on the changing needs at different stages. As more specialist roles are formalised, it is important to understand the environment that makes data science teams effective.

5. Long-term careers for specialist roles through permanent positions and targeted funding through leadership grants should be maintained, as exemplified by UKRI. This will elevate the professional status of specialist roles within institutions, fostering a resilient data science workforce.

The implementation of recommendations outlined in this policy briefing, targeted at national and institutional actors, including funders and policymakers, will strengthen the data science ecosystem. Specifically, diversifying and supporting specialist or RTP roles will empower institutions to prioritise responsible collaboration, peer-led innovation, and the equitable dissemination of technical solutions, ensuring a positive and sustainable impact of data science and AI.

Glossary

- **Open science** is the movement to make scientific research, including publications, data, physical samples, and software, as well as its dissemination accessible to all levels of society, amateur or professional.
- **Open source** is a process through which digital assets, such as source code are shared openly so that anyone can use, share, modify and build on without any price or access barriers.
- **Reproducibility** in research or data science means that the same analysis steps applied to the same dataset consistently yield identical results.
- **Reproducibility crisis** refers to the observation that many scientific studies are difficult or impossible to reproduce, highlighting a concern that a substantial portion of published research findings may not be reliable in several fields.
- **FAIR principles** provide a framework to ensure data and other digital objects such as software are made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- **Interdisciplinarity** involves two or more disciplines working together to solve problems or answer research questions that are beyond the scope of a single discipline. It requires cross-fertilisation between disciplines, building collaboration and a shared understanding of knowledge.
- **Team science** is a collaborative scientific approach that integrates the expertise of people from diverse disciplines to address complex problems.
- **Research Technical Professionals (RTPs)** bring knowledge and technical competence to their field, collaboratively maximising research effectiveness and individual potential within a team.

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